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ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF OBTAINING EDUCATION ABROAD (THE EXAMPLE OF UZBEKISTAN)

XORIJDA TA'LIM OLIISHNING AFZALLIKLARI VA KAMCHILIKLARI (O'ZBEKISTON MISOLIDA)

ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА И НЕДОСТАТКИ ПОЛУЧЕНИЯ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ ЗА РУБЕЖОМ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА)

Filimonova Liliya Yurevna [0000-0002-6707-937X]

Tashkent State Transport University, assistant of the department
Foreign Languages

Филимонова Лилия Юрьевна

Ташкентский государственный транспортный университет,
ассистент кафедры Иностранных языков

Filimonova Liliya Yuryevna

Toshkent davlat transport universiteti, Xorijiy tillar kafedrasini
asistenti

E-mail: victor_p54@mail.ru; **Phone:** +998933812706

Sobirova Guzal Rasuldjanovna [0009-0000-9890-1832]

Tashkent State Transport University, Student of group TNI -3r

Собирова Гузаль Расулжановна

Ташкентский государственный транспортный университет,
Студентка группы TNI-3р

Sobirova Guzal Rasuljonovna

Toshkent davlat transport universiteti, TNI-3r guruh talabasi

E-mail: callmeguzal@mail.ru; **Phone:** +998935582250

Abstract. This article explores the advantages and disadvantages of pursuing education abroad from the perspective of a student from Uzbekistan. Key benefits include access to high-quality education, exposure to diverse cultures, and improved language skills. However, challenges such as financial burdens, bureaucratic hurdles, cultural shock, and separation from family are significant drawbacks. The narrative highlights the decision-making process and personal reflections of a student who ultimately chose to study locally, emphasizing that quality education can also be found within Uzbekistan. The article underscores the importance of individual circumstances and goals in making educational choices.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonlik talaba nuqtai nazaridan chet elda ta'lim olishning afzalliklari va kamchiliklari o'rganiladi. Asosiy afzalliklarga sifatli ta'limga kirish, turli madaniyatlarga to'liq sho'ng'ish va til ko'nikmalarini yaxshilash kiradi. Biroq moliyaviy yuklar, byurokratik qiyinchiliklar, madaniy shok holati va oiladan uzoqlik kabi muammolar muhim kamchiliklarni tashkil etadi. Tajriba, talabaning qaror qabul qilish jarayonini va shaxsiy tafakkurlarini belgilaydi, natijada u sifatli ta'limni O'zbekistonda ham olish mumkinligini ta'kidlaydi. Maqolada ta'lim yo'lini tanlashda shaxsiy sharoitlar va maqsadlarning ahamiyati ta'kidlanadi.

Аннотация. Это статья исследует преимущества и недостатки получения образования за границей с точки зрения студентки из Узбекистана. Ключевые преимущества включают доступ к качественному образованию, погружение в разнообразные культуры и улучшение языковых навыков. Однако такие проблемы, как финансовые нагрузки, бюрократические трудности, культурный шок и разлука с семьей, являются значительными недостатками. Опыт подчеркивает процесс принятия решений и личные размышления студентки, которая в конечном итоге выбрала учёбу в своей стране, акцентируя внимание на том, что качественное образование также можно получить в Узбекистане. Статья подчеркивает важность индивидуальных обстоятельств и целей при выборе образовательного пути.

Keywords: education abroad, Uzbekistan, advantages, disadvantages, cultural shock, financial challenges, quality education.

Kalit so‘zlar: chet elda ta’lim, O‘zbekiston, afzalliklar, kamchiliklar, madaniy shok, moliyaviy qiyinchiliklar, sifatli ta’lim.

Ключевые слова: образование за границей, Узбекистан, преимущества, недостатки, культурный шок, финансовые трудности, качественное образование.

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Introduction. Education abroad is a dream for many students from Uzbekistan. The stereotype goes that most things far away from us should be better, more developed and interesting, though these are highly disputable issues.

In recent years, more and more young people have chosen this path, seeking quality education and international educational experience. However, like any important decision, it has its pros and cons, which should be considered based on personal experiences of the family members, parents, siblings and friends, and students' views. Having graduated from high school, the question of further education becomes especially urgent for all school leavers and for the authors of the article in particular. Dreams of getting a degree abroad come closer and it is a big question of consideration for the whole family, which fills a lot of minds and thoughts. Many imagine themselves studying at a famous university, meeting interesting people and trying to immerse in a foreign culture. However, beginning to research this topic in more detail, there can be encountered a number of disadvantages and difficulties that ultimately change the choice of many young people.

Personal experience of the student from Uzbekistan. When a plan was being developed to go to the university abroad, the youth is sure that it would give them the only opportunity to get a high-quality education and a unique experience. A lot of positive feedback from the students who studied in countries such as Germany, the USA and the UK has been heard. They talked about the high level of applying

modern teaching methods and technique, the opportunity to communicate with people from different cultures, societies and countries.

All these seemed very attractive to me. However, with the time coming nearer to be prepared for admission to university, we begin to realize that the path to the long cherished dream was not as easy as it could seem at the very first idea of studying abroad.

The first and most significant obstacle was the financial aspect. Studying abroad requires significant funds, and despite the availability of some scholarships and grants, we should clearly realize that those grants and scholarships would not be able to fully cover the costs of tuition, using books from the library and buying them, besides covering of living expenses. This puts a lot of pressure on the idea of choosing a university abroad, and serious worries begin to appear that the dream might remain just a dream.

Moreover, the process of obtaining various documents, first of which being the proof of the English language knowledge certificate, and a visa processing turns out to be very confusing. Bureaucratic difficulties faced by any candidate to study abroad sometimes seem insurmountable.

With each new step, there increasingly comes understanding that in order to achieve the goal of acquiring a foreign university degree, it would be necessary to overcome not only financial but also administrative barriers.

Another thing to realize is that living in another country can be associated with cultural shock. Despite common dream of traveling and experiencing new things and emotions, adapting to the new environment could be challenging.

Uzbekistan is a country of the family-based society, where the whole life of its citizens depends on the family, their traditions, customs and rites, centuries proved ideals, respect of the elder generation and its advice and expertise. Separation from the family and friends also makes family supervised teenagers anxious. We should be prepared, that there will be no support of the family and missing this support of the loved ones during initial period of difficult times, as all beginnings are really troublesome, this can create cultural and social shock and additional stress.

Ultimately, very important conclusions were made. Studying abroad has its undeniable advantages, such as the opportunity to immerse in a new culture, get to know unfamiliar social traditions and way of life, meet new people and gain international experience.

However, along with this, there are also significant disadvantages that can influence the student's choice. Personal experience, financial constraints, and adaptation to a new environment all play a significant role in the decision-making process.

Today, taking into account all above mentioned factors, the author can be proud of choosing the path that matches personal capabilities and aspirations. That education received in Uzbekistan can none the less become a solid foundation for a successful career. Each student must find his/her own path based on their goals and circumstances.

Literature review. The amount of literature sources concerning getting education not only in the native country of birth, but also abroad is really tremendous. Most developed countries are for providing education for their citizens and foreign students. The aim of European and American universities is head hunting [5]. They are eventually looking for potential young scientific forces. Because of that language acquisition certificate demands are according to the needs of universities. Students can present one of the language certificates from the long list, they all are transferable.

Legal documents of Uzbekistan support the idea of getting education in general and free choice of profession by any young man or woman. It is stated in the new edition of Constitution and the Law on Education [3, 2].

President of Uzbekistan constantly keeps in touch with representatives of education sphere, takes part in discussions, conferences, presentations. The presentation, dated May 23, 2024 discusses key areas for reforming the education system, emphasizing the importance of quality education and qualified personnel training for the future development of the economics of Uzbekistan [1].

Research methodology: benefits of a foreign university degree obtaining a foreign university degree can significantly expand career opportunities for students from Uzbekistan. Let's take a closer look at how exactly this happens and what benefits studying abroad provides.

- Degrees from renowned foreign universities are often recognized internationally, which increases the chances of employment both in Uzbekistan and abroad. Companies operating in the global market prefer candidates providing their education degree from prestigious universities. It is taken for granted that this indicates a high level of training and skills.

- In the context of increasing competition in the labor market, presenting a degree from a foreign university can become a significant competitive advantage in the native country later. Employers often look for candidates with international experience, as they can bring new ideas and approaches to the organization. This is especially true for areas such as information technology, finance and management.

- Studying at a foreign university often includes participation in projects, internships and practicums, which allow students to develop practical skills necessary for their future work. At foreign universities there are always lists of optional courses and clubs, beginning from communication or writing skills up to IT technologies. These additional educational opportunities provide students with real-world experience that can be very valuable to employers.

Analysis and results. Adapting to life in another country: challenges and examples. Living in another country can be both an exciting and difficult experience. Adapting to new conditions takes time effort, and students often face various difficulties, which can be both connected with everyday life and social one.

One of the first challenges that students face is looking for housing. Depending on the country and city, rental prices can vary greatly, and finding a suitable place can be difficult. Students may find themselves in a situation where they need to make a quick decision about housing, which adds stress. In addition, everyday habits and

culture of the two countries and two peoples can be very different from the expected ones. For example, students may encounter different rules of behavior, traditions and customs. This can concern both everyday life and generally accepted norms of communication. Misunderstanding of local customs can lead to awkward situations or even conflicts.

Social adaptation is also a significant challenge. Students may experience a feeling of loneliness and isolation, especially at the beginning of their studies. Making friends and establishing social connections can become a long-term process, especially if a student does not have the sufficient command of the language of the country.

The vivid example of the difficulties students may face is one of the situations recently published in the comments of the education sites. A student from Bangladesh asked a question but did not receive any answer because other students from Uzbekistan were unable to help him due to the language barrier, their low level of language proficiency. This highlights how important language communication is in the learning environment.

When students cannot understand each other, it not only makes it difficult to solve problems, but also hinders the formation of good relations and friendship. The language barrier can be a real obstacle to integration into a new environment, and many students may feel alienated from their fellow students.

It is important to use the resources available to the entrees to successfully adapt in the new place and new country. Many universities offer support programs for international students, including language courses and interest groups. Participating in such programs can help students not only improve their language skills, but also make new friends. In addition, students can look for communities where they can connect with other international students who are facing similar difficulties. This can create a sense of belonging to the same social group and reduce psychological stress.

Fig. 1. Pros and Cons Ratio

The pie-chart shows us that there are still more advantages than drawbacks of obtaining education abroad according to our public opinion and authors' research. However, usually there are plenty of new issues for consideration on returning of the Bachelors and Masters home. They are the best representatives of our young

generation, but they have missed several years of their life in the country. Therefore, they again have to undergo the period of adjusting back to our country realities and present-day situation, first of all, in education sphere, and in economics, politics, culture and social life. From the point of view of educators, too much time is spent on these two periods of adaptation, this time of the young generation could be used more usefully and productively in our native country for both training and practicing of the professionally acquired skills [6].

Conclusion and recommendations. Educating abroad is an important and multifaceted process that opens up many opportunities, but also comes with certain challenges. Students seeking international experience face both advantages, such as improved career prospects, development of personal and professional skills, and disadvantages, including financial costs, cultural shock, and adjustment difficulties. Several of the easiest advise, how to overcome only some of the possible difficulties are:

1) not only to start learning English for getting the language certificate, but also general or everyday English to facilitate situation of communication with local people of the country, as most citizens will have no language certificates, which means, they are going to communicate with you using colloquial and oral English only;

2) to find out what language certificates are available in the country of your supposed future education. For example, in Turkey you can only present TOEFL or local language certificate, as they do not accept IELTS certificate at all;

3) to start travelling. If, possible to visit the country you are going to choose for your forthcoming education. Finding this impossible due to some reasons, the future student should travel around and visit at least other regions of our country or our neighboring countries. This also will give positive experience, overlook of new places and people or peoples, understanding their culture and behavior.

Adapting to new living conditions takes time and effort. Students must be prepared to seek support and use available resources to successfully integrate into a new cultural environment and establish social connections. Examples such as the situation with international students highlight the importance of language communication and mutual assistance in the learning process.

Ultimately, when deciding to study abroad, it is important to very carefully evaluate all the pros and cons, taking into account personal goals and circumstances. Taking into account all the pluses and drawbacks, this experience can be a significant step towards personal and professional growth, opening up new horizons and opportunities for a future career.

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